

CRITICAL SPEEDS OF POLAR ORTHOTROPIC ANNULAR DISKS IN ROTATION

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SUMMARY: In this paper, an application of composite materials to rotating disks is proposed to increase the critical speed. Dynamic equation is formulated in order to calculate the natural frequency and critical speed for rotating composite disks by the Rayleigh-Ritz method. The orthogonal functions are used for series solution. Fibers could be aligned in radial or circumferential directions to have polar orthotropy in circular disk. The results show that the radially reinforced disk is more effective in increasing critical speed than the circumferentially reinforced disk. The radially reinforced CFRP CD is shown to have the five times higher critical speed than that of the polycarbonate CD.

KEYWORDS: critical speed, polar orthotropic disk, rotating disks, vibration, CD.

INTRODUCTION

Rotating annular disks are widely used in data storage devices such as CDs, DVDs(digital versatile disks), and HDs(hard disks) as well as in machines such as circular saws, turbines, and so on. The demand for higher data transfer rate in computers causes a drastic increase of rotating speed in CD-ROM drives. The 52× (52 times the transfer rate of the original CD-ROM) CD-ROM drives of which rotating speed is 7,000 to 10,000 rpm prevail in the market. However, the 52× is expected to be the last polycarbonate CD because its lowest critical speed is around 7,000 rpm [1]. This barrier can be breached by applying fiber-reinforce composite materials to CD. The backward travelling wave becomes stationary at the critical speed in non-rotating frame and a disk is destabilized by stationary transverse load.

The vibration analysis of rotating isotropic disks has attracted much attention since Lamb and Southwell [2] dealt with this problem. However, there are not many papers on the vibration characteristics on rotating composite disks [3-6]. Ghosh [3] did not provide the vibration characteristics of rotating orthotropic disk. Son, *et al.* [4, 5] applied their method only to the laminated disk composed of polycarbonate and aluminium layers. Liang, *et al.* [6] investigated natural frequencies and stability of a rotating polar orthotropic disk subject to a stationary concentrated transverse load. The material property they used is not realistic because the Poisson's ratio $\nu_{12} = -\varepsilon_2/\varepsilon_1$ can have a negative value. According to their results, the natural frequencies increase to infinity when the modulus ratio E_θ/E_r equals nine. However, it is not true and they should the correct formulae for the in-plane membrane stresses.

An application of polar orthotropic materials to rotating disk is proposed in this paper to increase the critical speed of CD. Fibbers in circular disk could be aligned in radial or

circumferential directions to have polar orthotropy. In the present paper, the vibration problem of rotating annular disk of polar orthotropic materials is formulated. The Rayleigh-Ritz method using orthogonal polynomial functions is applied to get the critical speeds. The result shows that the application of polar orthotropic material to rotating disk is very successful in increasing the critical speed.

GOVERNING EQUATIONS

Polar orthotropic disks can be made by aligning fibers in radial or circumferential directions on disk as shown in Fig. 1.

Fig. 1: (a) Radially-reinforced and (b) circumferentially-reinforced composite disks

The stress-strain relations for polar orthotropic materials under plane stress are

$$\begin{Bmatrix} \varepsilon_r \\ \varepsilon_\theta \\ \gamma_{r\theta} \end{Bmatrix} = \begin{bmatrix} 1/E_r & -\nu_{\theta r}/E_\theta & 0 \\ -\nu_{r\theta}/E_r & 1/E_\theta & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & G_{r\theta} \end{bmatrix} \begin{Bmatrix} \sigma_r \\ \sigma_\theta \\ \tau_{r\theta} \end{Bmatrix} \quad (1)$$

where r and θ denote the radial and circumferential directions, respectively; and $\nu_{r\theta}/E_r = \nu_{\theta r}/E_\theta$.

Two polar coordinate systems are introduced for the description of a rotating disk with thickness h as shown in Fig. 2. The (r, θ) coordinate rotates at a constant speed Ω fixed to the disk and the (r, ϕ) coordinate does not rotate fixed in the inertial space. The disk is assumed to be sufficiently thin so that the transverse shear deformation and rotary inertia may be neglected.

The displacements of the disk in the (r, θ) coordinate can expressed by

$$u_r = u_r^0 - z \frac{\partial w}{\partial r}, \quad u_\theta = u_\theta^0 - z \frac{\partial w}{r \partial \theta}, \quad w = w \quad (2)$$

Fig. 2: Coordinates and geometry of rotating disk

where the subscript 0 denotes the mid-plane.

The bending strain energy for the orthotropic disk can be expressed by

$$U_b = \frac{1}{2} \int_b^a \int_0^{2\pi} \boldsymbol{\kappa}^T \mathbf{D} \boldsymbol{\kappa} r dr d\theta \quad (3)$$

where

$$\boldsymbol{\kappa} = \begin{Bmatrix} \kappa_r \\ \kappa_\theta \\ \kappa_{r\theta} \end{Bmatrix}, \quad \mathbf{D} = \begin{bmatrix} D_r & D_{r\theta} & 0 \\ D_{r\theta} & D_\theta & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & D_k \end{bmatrix} \quad (4)$$

The elements of the middle surface curvature $\boldsymbol{\kappa}$ and the bending stiffness \mathbf{D} are defined by

$$\kappa_r = \frac{\partial^2 w}{\partial r^2}, \quad \kappa_\theta = \frac{\partial w}{r \partial r} + \frac{\partial w}{r^2 \partial \theta^2}, \quad \kappa_{r\theta} = 2 \frac{\partial}{\partial r} \left(\frac{\partial w}{r \partial \theta} \right) \quad (5.a)$$

$$D_r = \frac{E_r h^3}{12(1-\nu_{r\theta}\nu_{\theta r})}, \quad D_\theta = \frac{E_\theta h^3}{12(1-\nu_{r\theta}\nu_{\theta r})}, \quad D_{r\theta} = \nu_{r\theta} D_\theta, \quad D_k = \frac{G_{r\theta} h^3}{12} \quad (5.b)$$

The strain energy due to the membrane stresses caused by rotation is given by

$$U_\Omega = \frac{1}{2} \int_b^a \int_0^{2\pi} \left\{ \bar{N}_r \left(\frac{\partial w}{\partial r} \right)^2 + \bar{N}_\theta \left(\frac{\partial w}{r \partial \theta} \right)^2 + 2 \bar{N}_{r\theta} \frac{\partial w}{\partial r} \frac{\partial w}{r \partial \theta} \right\} r dr d\theta \quad (6)$$

where \bar{N}_r , \bar{N}_θ , and $\bar{N}_{r\theta}$ are the resultant forces per unit length.

Since all derivatives of membrane displacements with respect to θ vanish for axisymmetric situation, \bar{N}_r , \bar{N}_θ , and $\bar{N}_{r\theta}$ are expressed by

$$\bar{N}_r = K_r \frac{d\bar{u}_r}{dr} + \nu_{r\theta} K_\theta \frac{\bar{u}_r}{r}, \quad \bar{N}_\theta = \nu_{\theta r} K_r \frac{d\bar{u}_r}{dr} + K_\theta \frac{\bar{u}_r}{r}, \quad \bar{N}_{r\theta} = hG \left(-\frac{\bar{u}_\theta}{r} + \frac{d\bar{u}_\theta}{dr} \right) \quad (7)$$

where \bar{u}_r denotes a membrane displacement in radial direction; $K_r = E_r h / (1 - \nu_{r\theta}\nu_{\theta r})$ and $K_\theta = E_\theta h / (1 - \nu_{r\theta}\nu_{\theta r})$. In Eqn. 7, $\bar{N}_{r\theta}$ vanishes when a disk rotates at constant speed.

The forces \bar{N}_r and \bar{N}_θ can be determined from the equation of motion in r -direction:

$$-\frac{\partial}{\partial r} (r \bar{N}_r) - \frac{\partial \bar{N}_{r\theta}}{\partial \theta} + \bar{N}_\theta = r(\rho r \Omega^2) \quad (8)$$

where ρ is the density of the disk and $\partial \bar{N}_{r\theta} / \partial \theta = 0$ for axisymmetric problem.

Substitution of the forces in Eqn. 7 into Eqn. 8 yields

$$r^2 \frac{d^2 \bar{u}_r}{dr^2} + r \frac{d\bar{u}_r}{dr} - \mu^2 \bar{u}_r = -\frac{\rho h \Omega^2 r^3}{K_r} \quad (9)$$

where $\mu^2 = E_\theta / E_r$. The disk fixed at inner radius b and free at outer radius a has the following boundary conditions:

$$\bar{u}_r|_{r=b} = 0, \quad \bar{N}_r|_{r=a} = 0 \quad (10)$$

Substituting the solution of Eqn. 9 satisfying the boundary conditions into Eqn. 8 gives

$$\begin{aligned} \bar{N}_r &= k \left\{ (C_{r1} - \delta_{\mu 3}) r^{\mu-1} - \frac{C_{r2}}{r^{\mu+1}} - C_{r3} r^2 g(r) \right\} \rho h \Omega^2 \\ \bar{N}_\theta &= k \left\{ (C_{\theta 1} - \nu_{r\theta} \delta_{\mu 3}) r^{\mu-1} - \frac{C_{\theta 2}}{r^{\mu+1}} - C_{\theta 3} r^2 g(r) \right\} \rho h \Omega^2 \end{aligned} \quad (11)$$

where $\delta_{\mu 3}$ is the Kronecker delta and the other constants are defined as

$$\begin{cases} k = 1/(9 - \mu^2), & g(r) = 1 & \text{for } \mu \neq 3 \\ k = 1/6, & g(r) = \ln r & \text{for } \mu = 3 \end{cases} \quad (12.a)$$

$$C_{r1} = C_{\theta 1} / \mu = (1 + \mu \nu_{r\theta}) [(3 + \nu_{\theta r}) g(a) + \delta_{\mu 3} a^3 b^{-\mu} + (\mu - \nu_{\theta r}) g(b) a^{-\mu} b^3] / D \quad (12.b)$$

$$C_{r2} = C_{\theta 2} / \mu = \{(\mu + \nu_{\theta r}) g(a) - (3 + \nu_{\theta r}) g(b) + \delta_{\mu 3} a^\mu b^3\} / D \quad (12.c)$$

$$C_{r3} = 3 + \nu_{\theta r}, \quad C_{\theta 3} = \mu^2 (1 + 3 \nu_{\theta r}) \quad (12.d)$$

$$D = (1 + \mu \nu_{r\theta}) (a/b)^\mu + (1 - \mu \nu_{r\theta}) (b/a)^\mu \quad (12.e)$$

The kinetic energy due to the lateral vibration of the disk can be given by

$$T = \frac{1}{2} \int_b^a \int_0^{2\pi} \rho h \left(\frac{\partial w}{\partial t} \right)^2 r dr d\theta \quad (13)$$

Assuming the lateral displacement $w(r, \theta, t) = \sum_{i=1}^N q_i(t) f_i(r) \cos(n\theta)$ in U_b , U_Ω and T , the Lagrange equation yields

$$\mathbf{M}\ddot{\mathbf{q}} + (\mathbf{K}^b + \Omega^2 \mathbf{K}^\Omega) \mathbf{q} = \mathbf{0} \quad (14)$$

where the mass and stiffness matrices are defined by

$$M_{ij} = \rho h \int_b^a f_i f_j r dr \quad (15)$$

$$\begin{aligned} K_{ij}^b &= \int_b^a \{ D_r f_i'' f_j'' r + D_{r\theta} (f_i'' f_j' + f_i' f_j'') - n^2 D_{r\theta} (f_i'' f_j + f_i f_j'') \frac{1}{r} + (D_\theta + 4n^2 D_k) f_i' f_j' \frac{1}{r} \\ &\quad - n^2 (D_\theta + 4D_k) (f_i' f_j + f_i f_j') \frac{1}{r^2} + n^2 (n^2 D_\theta + 4D_k) f_i f_j \frac{1}{r^3} \} dr \end{aligned} \quad (16)$$

$$K_{ij}^{\Omega} = \rho h k \int_b^a \{[(C_{r1} - \delta_{\mu 3})r^{\mu} - C_{r2}r^{-\mu} - C_{r2}r^3 g(r)]f_i' f_j' + n^2 \{(C_{\theta 1} - \nu_{\theta r} \delta_{\mu 3})r^{\mu-2} + C_{\theta 2}r^{-\mu-2} - C_{\theta 3}r^2 g(r)\}f_i f_j\} dr \quad (17)$$

where a prime denotes differentiation with respect to r .

Assuming the solution of Eqn. 14 to be $q = \bar{q}e^{i\omega t}$, the natural frequencies in the rotating coordinate (r, θ) can be computed. The natural frequencies in the stationary coordinate (r, ϕ) can be determined from the governing equation

$$K[w] + \rho h \left(\frac{\partial^2 w}{\partial t^2} + 2\Omega \frac{\partial^2 w}{\partial t \partial \phi} + \Omega^2 \frac{\partial^2 w}{\partial \phi^2} \right) = 0 \quad (18)$$

where K is the linear differential operator for stiffness. Then assuming the solution of Eqn. 18 to be $w = R(r)\cos(n\phi)e^{\lambda t}$, the relationship between the natural frequencies in the rotating coordinate and stationary coordinate is expressed as

$$\lambda_{mn}^2 + i2n\Omega\lambda_{mn} + (\omega_{mn}^2 - n^2\Omega^2), \quad \lambda_{mn} = \begin{cases} -i(\omega_{mn} + n\Omega) \\ i(\omega_{mn} - n\Omega) \end{cases} \quad (19)$$

where $\omega_{mn} + n\Omega$ is the natural frequency of forward traveling wave and $\omega_{mn} - n\Omega$ is the natural frequency of backward traveling wave. The m and n in Eqn. (19) denote the number of nodal circles and diameters, respectively.

The frequency of the backward traveling wave becomes zero at certain rotation speeds which are called critical speeds. At this situation, the propagation speed of a backward traveling wave in the rotating frame is equal to the disk rotation speed. It means the backward traveling wave is stationary in the inertial frame at critical speed. A stationary transverse load applied to the disk at critical speeds would cause the amplitude of transverse motion to be unbounded without any damping mechanism.

The accuracy of the solution of Eqn. 14 depends on the choice of the functions $f_i(r)$ Eqns. 15-17. The functions $f_i(r) = (r-b)^{i+1}$ as a solution have been tried but did not give good results when the higher order functions, $i > 4$ were used. The orthogonal polynomial functions proposed by Bhat [7] are used to have a stable solution for the higher order functions, $i > 4$. These functions were applied successfully to the lateral vibration of thin annular and circular composite plates by Kim and Dickinson [8].

The first function $f_1(\xi)$ is written in a normalised coordinate $\xi = r/a$ as

$$f_1(\xi) = \sum_{k=1}^5 a_k \xi^{k-1} \quad (20)$$

where the coefficients a_k are

$$a_1 = c^2(6 - 8c + 3c^2), \quad a_2 = -4c(3 - 3c + c^2), \quad a_3 = 6, \quad a_4 = -4, \quad a_5 = 1, \quad c = b/a \quad (21)$$

The orthogonal condition $\int_c^1 \xi f_k(\xi) f_l(\xi) d\xi = F_{kl} \delta_{kl}$ where F_{kl} is a constant creates the next functions $f_k(\xi)$, $k \geq 2$ as follows:

$$f_{k+1}(\xi) = (\xi - b_k)f_k(\xi) - c_k f_{k-1}(\xi) \quad (22)$$

where

$$f_0(\xi) \equiv 0, \quad b_k = \int_c^1 \xi^2 f_k^2(\xi) d\xi / \int_c^1 \xi f_k^2(\xi) d\xi, \quad c_k = \int_c^1 \xi f_k^2(\xi) d\xi / \int_c^1 \xi f_{k-1}^2(\xi) d\xi \quad (23)$$

RESULTS AND DISCUSSIONS

The rotating disks are assumed to have the same dimension as those of CD-ROM where $b = 15$ mm, $a = 60$ mm, $t = 1.2$ mm. Three materials shown in Table 1 are selected to calculate the natural frequencies and critical speeds of the rotating disks. CD-ROM is made of polycarbonate. The material properties of E-glass/Epoxy and T300/N5208 are used as typical properties of GFRP(Glass Fiber Reinforced Plastics) and CFRP(Glass Fiber Reinforced Plastics), respectively.

Table 1: Material properties

Material	E_1 (GPa)	E_2 (GPa)	G_{12} (GPa)	ν_{12}	ρ (kg/m ³)
Polycarbonate CD	2.2	2.2	0.846	0.30	1220
GFRP(E-glass/Epoxy)	38.6	8.27	4.14	0.26	1800
CFRP(T300/N5208)	181.0	10.3	7.17	0.28	1600

Polycarbonate CD

The vibration analysis of polycarbonate CD has been performed in order to validate the developed formulation. The natural frequencies of non-rotating CD given in Table 2 are shown to be in a good agreement with those in Ref. 9.

Fig. 3 shows the natural frequencies of rotating CD in order of the lowest critical speeds. In Fig. 3, $(m,n)f$ and $(m,n)b$ mean the forward and backward natural frequencies, respectively, with m nodal circles and n nodal diameters. The lowest critical speed where the backward natural frequency becomes zero is about 7,060 rpm in mode (0,2). It is found that the five lowest critical modes are those with no nodal circles, namely, the modes $(0,n)$. Therefore, it can be inferred from the results in Fig. 3 that reinforcing a disk in the circumferential

Table 2: Natural frequencies(Hz) of non-rotating CD

m	n	0	1	2	3	4	5
0	Present	125.9	121.0	153.2	277.2	472.5	722.3
	Ref. 9	125.9	120.9	153.1	277.1	472.6	723.1
1	Present	796.5	842.5	990.2	1254.6	1634.0	2110.0
	Ref. 9	796.1	842.0	988.9	1251.4	1627.9	2099.7
2	Present	2348	2404	2577	2884	3335	3927
	Ref. 9	2313	2369	2543	2851	3303	3894
3	Present	4680	4745	4946	5304	5852	6629
	Ref. 9	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA
4	Present	20322	20350	20434	20578	20787	21070
	Ref. 9	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA

Fig. 3: Frequency-speed diagram for PC CD

direction can effectively increase critical speeds. Reinforcing a disk in the radial direction also is expected to increase the critical speed since it makes the natural frequencies higher. In next sections, the influence of fiber alignment on critical speeds is studied for GFRP and CFRP disks.

GFRP DISKS

As aforementioned, the radially-reinforced(RR) and circumferentially-reinforced(CR) disks are considered as polar orthotropic disks to increase the lowest critical speed of CD. For those two types of disks, the material constants should be assigned in the following ways:

$$\text{RR disk: } E_r = E_1, E_\theta = E_2, G_{r\theta} = G_{12}, \nu_{r\theta} = \nu_{12}$$

$$\text{CR disk: } E_r = E_2, E_\theta = E_1, G_{r\theta} = G_{12}, \nu_{r\theta} = \nu_{21}$$

Fig. 4 shows the frequency-speed diagram for the RR GFRP disk. The natural frequencies of modes (0,0) and (0,1) are very similar. The RR GFRP disk has the lowest critical speed at 12,529 rpm in mode (0,3). It is noted that the critical mode is (0,3) for the RR GFRP disk while the polycarbonate disk is critical in mode (0,2).

The frequency-speed diagram for the CR GFRP disk is plotted in Fig. 5. A thorough comparison of the natural frequencies of stationary disks in Figs. 4 and 5 reveals that the CR GFRP disk has rather higher natural frequencies in modes (0,3), (0,4) and (0,5). The lowest critical speed occurs at 18,462 rpm in mode (0,2). The lowest critical speed of the CR GFRP disk is 2.6 times as fast as that of the polycarbonate disk.

Fig. 4: Frequency-speed diagram for RR GFRP disk

Fig. 5: Frequency-speed diagram for CR GFRP disk.

CFRP DISKS

In general, CFRP materials have much higher E_1 than GFRP materials as shown in Table 1. Both the RR and CR disks are considered for the CFRP disks as the GFRP disks.

Figs. 6 and 7 show the frequency-speed diagram of the RR and CR CFRP disks, respectively. The natural frequencies of the non-rotating CFRP disks are much higher than those of the GFRP disks. The lowest critical speed of the RR CFRP is 19,105 rpm. The critical mode is (0,4) because the natural frequency of mode (0,4) is not much higher than those of lower modes and the effect of radial stiffening of the rotating disk in mode (0,4) is relatively small.

It is seen in Fig. 7 that the non-rotating CR CFRP disk has the frequency of mode (0,2) lower than that of mode (0,0) unlike the other disk. The modes (0,3), (0,4), and (0,5) of the CR disk have higher natural frequencies than those of the RR disk and the CR CFRP disk, compared to the RR CFRP disk, has more effect of radial stiffening. These phenomena make the critical speeds of the CR CFRP disk be increased very much higher. The CR CFRP disk has the lowest critical speed at 40,218 rpm in mode (0,2). This speed is the highest among those considered in this paper.

Table 2 summarizes the lowest critical speeds and modes of the disks dealt with in this paper.

Fig. 6: Frequency-speed diagram for RR CFRP disk

Fig. 7: Frequency-speed diagram for CR CFRP disk

Table 2: Critical speeds and modes

Parameter	PC CD	RR GFRP	CR GFRP	RR CFRP	CR CFRP
Speed(rpm)	7,060	12,529	18,462	19,106	40,218
Mode	(0,2)	(0,3)	(0,2)	(0,4)	(0,2)

CONCLUSIONS

Although the market needs faster disk drives for higher data transfer rate in computers, the rotating speed in disk drives is stagnated in 7,000 to 10,000 rpm. In this paper, an application of composite materials to CD has been attempted to increase the critical speed.

The vibration equation of the rotating disks composed of polar orthotropic materials is derived by the energy method. The Rayleigh-Ritz method was used with orthogonal polynomial functions for accurate results.

The critical speeds of the typical GFRP and CFRP CD are computed by aligning the fibers in radial or circumferential directions. The result shows that the application of polar orthotropic material to rotating disk is very successful in increasing the critical speed. Moreover, the radially-reinforced CFRP CD is shown to have the five times higher critical speed than that of the polycarbonate CD.

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